

FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION IN A SELF-HEALING POLYMER COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

A novel approach is explored for improving the fatigue life of thermosetting polymers through the addition of *self-healing functionality*. Thermosetting polymers are used in a wide variety of applications ranging from composite structures to adhesive joints to microelectronic packaging. Due to their low strain-to-failure these polymers are highly susceptible to damage in the form of cracks. Fatigue loading is particularly problematic, giving rise to the initiation and propagation of small cracks deep within the structure where detection is difficult and repair is virtually impossible. These cracks often lead to catastrophic failure of the material. We utilize a strategy based on recent developments in self-healing technology to *autonomically* repair fatigue cracks and extend the service-life of many polymeric components. The material under investigation is an epoxy matrix composite, which utilizes embedded microcapsules to store a healing agent and an embedded catalyst. A propagating crack exposes particles of catalyst and ruptures the microcapsules, which release healing agent into the crack plane. Polymerization of the healing agent is triggered by contact with the catalyst, which bonds the crack faces closed.

A comprehensive experimental program is carried-out to assess the fatigue behavior of a self-healing polymer. The testing program has two primary thrusts. The first is to obtain the inherent fatigue characteristics of the matrix material. In this case the ability to self-heal and the self-healing effects on the fatigue behavior are precluded. Here we embed unfilled microcapsules (no healing agent) along with the catalyst in the epoxy matrix. In tandem we formulate two types of controls: unfilled epoxy and embedded microcapsules alone. The second testing thrust is to characterize the fatigue characteristics of the self-healing materials system. This presents a considerable challenge in managing the multitude of interaction variables that are operative such as stress amplitude, frequency, *in situ* healing rate, rest period and frequency. Fatigue crack propagation in neat epoxy and epoxy with embedded microcapsules is accurately captured by the Paris power-law. The slope n of the power-law regime is strongly dependent on the content of microcapsules, varying from $n = 10$ for neat epoxy to $n = 4$ for 10 wt% microcapsules. The inherent fatigue characteristics of the self-healing material and its ability to extend component life are currently being investigated.

INTRODUCTION

Self-healing materials are inspired by living systems, in which minor damage (*e.g.*, a bump or bruise) triggers an autonomic healing response. In biological systems, chemical signals released at the site of fracture initiate a systemic response that transports repair agents to the site of injury and promotes

healing. In recent research at the University of Illinois [1], we have successfully engineered a self-healing epoxy, which mimics many of the features of a biological system. Healing is accomplished by incorporating a microencapsulated healing agent and a catalytic chemical trigger within a polymer matrix. Damage in the form of a crack serves as the triggering mechanism for self-healing as does the fracture event in biological systems. The approaching crack ruptures the embedded microcapsules, releasing healing agent into the crack plane through capillary action. Polymerization of the healing agent is triggered by contact with the embedded catalyst, bonding the crack faces. As with biological systems, this triggering mechanism provides site-specific control of healing. An additional unique feature of our healing concept is the use of *living* polymerization catalysts (*i.e.*, having unterminated chains), thus enabling multiple healing events. Repair of hidden damage in a material is accomplished automatically and without human intervention, improving performance and service-life.

Our research to date has focused on selection of the appropriate chemistry, perfecting the triggering mechanism, and developing an effective protocol to assess healing efficiency. Conclusive demonstration of self-healing was obtained with a healing agent based on the ring-opening metathesis polymerization (ROMP) reaction [1,2]. Dicyclopentadiene (DCPD), a highly stable monomer with excellent shelf life, was encapsulated in microcapsules with 0.5-micron thick shell made of urea formaldehyde. A small volume fraction of microcapsules was dispersed in an epoxy resin along with a transition metal (Grubbs') catalyst, a living catalyst that remains reactive after triggering the polymerization reaction. The embedded microcapsules were shown to rupture in the presence of a crack and release the DCPD monomer into the crack plane. Contact with the embedded Grubbs' catalyst initiated polymerization of the DCPD and rebonded the crack plane. This self-healing epoxy is able to recover over 90% of its virgin fracture toughness [2].

In addition to providing an efficient mechanism for self-healing, the presence of DCPD-filled UF microcapsules also increases the inherent fracture toughness of the epoxy. Under monotonic loading the average maximum toughness with microcapsules is 127% greater than neat epoxy. Fracture of the neat epoxy is brittle, exhibiting a mirror fracture surface. The addition of microcapsules produces a transition of the fracture plane morphology to hackle markings. The increased toughening associated with fluid-filled microcapsules is attributed to increased hackle marking and subsurface microcracking not observed for solid particle fillers [3]. While fracture toughness is an important property for evaluating self-healing performance, fatigue loading is particularly problematic in brittle polymers. The current investigation seeks to apply recent breakthroughs in self-healing technology to repair fatigue cracks in a polymer autonomically.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The fatigue crack propagation behavior of microcapsule-filled epoxy was investigated using a tapered double-cantilever beam (TDCB) test. Side grooves ensured controlled crack growth along the centerline of the brittle specimen. The TDCB geometry, developed by Mostovoy et al. [4], provided a crack-length-independent relationship between applied stress intensity factor K_I and load P ,

$$K_I = \alpha P, \quad (1)$$

which only required knowledge of the geometric term α . For the TDCB sample geometry in Fig. 1, $\alpha = 11.2 \times 10^3 \text{ m}^{-3/2}$ was determined experimentally as discussed by Brown et al. [2].

Figure 1 Tapered double-cantilever beam (TDCB) geometry [2].

Urea-formaldehyde microcapsules containing DCPD monomer were manufactured with diameters of $53 \pm 19 \mu\text{m}$ and $183 \pm 43 \mu\text{m}$ using the emulsion in situ polymerization microencapsulation method outlined by Brown et al [5]. Shell wall thickness was $190 \pm 30 \text{ nm}$ for all batches. Tapered double-cantilever beam specimens were cast from EPON[®] 828 epoxy resin (DGEBA) and 12 pph Ancamine[®] DETA (diethylenetriamine) curing agent with a prescribed concentration of microcapsules and catalyst. The epoxy mixture was degassed, poured into a closed silicone rubber mold and cured for 24 hours at room temperature, followed by 24 hours at 30°C . A razor blade was gently tapped into a molded starter notch to generate a sharp precrack.

EFFECT OF MICROCAPSULES ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH

The addition of self-healing functionality, *i.e.* microcapsules and catalyst, must not detrimentally affect the virgin fatigue performance. We first characterized the inherent fatigue characteristics of the matrix material with varying concentrations of microcapsules but no catalyst, so that the ability to self-heal and any self-healing effects on the fatigue behavior were precluded.

The effect of embedded microcapsule size and concentration on fatigue crack growth is shown in Fig. 3. The relationship between crack growth rate, da/dN , and the applied range of Mode-I stress intensity factor, ΔK_I , is consistent with the Paris-Power Law,

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C_o \Delta K_I^n, \quad (2)$$

where C_o and n are material dependent constants. Crack propagation in neat Epon 828/DETA (no microcapsules) yields a Paris exponent of $n = 9.7$. This value is consistent with previous values reported in the literature for epoxy [6-8]. With the addition of microcapsules a distinct transition point is observed, below which microcapsules do not affect fatigue crack growth rate. Above this threshold, approximately $\Delta K_I = 0.4 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$, epoxy with microcapsules exhibits a higher resistance to fatigue crack growth than neat epoxy, accompanied by a reduction of the Paris Law exponent n . The observed reduction of n with microcapsule concentration above the transition is independent of microcapsule diameter (Fig. 4). For concentrations greater than 10 wt% microcapsules, n has a steady state value of approximately 4.5. Similar fatigue behavior has been reported for rubber toughened epoxy [8]. The addition of microcapsules significantly extends the fatigue life of the epoxy.

Figure 3. The effect of microcapsule concentration on the FCP behavior.

Figure 4. The effect of microcapsule concentration on Paris Law exponent, n .

EFFECT OF SELF-HEALING ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH

Once the fatigue characteristics of epoxy with microcapsules were established, the effects of self-healing on fatigue crack growth were investigated. Fatigue tests were carried out on self-healing samples with 20 wt% microcapsules and 2.5 wt% catalyst. To show the effect of self-healing more clearly, crack tip position is plotted versus number of cycles in Fig. 6. Fatigue crack growth was arrested for 4×10^5 cycles in the self-healing sample, extending the fatigue life over 3 times that of the control sample with no self-healing [5]. Although preliminary, the data in Fig. 6 indicate that self-healing functionality significantly enhances fatigue life and has the potential to increase overall reliability of a structure.

Fig. 6 Crack tip position versus number of cycles to failure for self healing sample compared to control.

CONCLUSIONS

Fatigue crack propagation behavior in a self-healing epoxy was investigated. First, the ability to self-heal was precluded and experiments focused on the effect of the embedded microcapsules (with no catalyst) on fatigue performance. Above a distinct transition point, the addition of microcapsules effectively retarded fatigue crack growth and extended the overall fatigue life. Once the fatigue characteristics of epoxy with microcapsules were established, the effects of self-healing on fatigue crack growth were investigated. The addition of self-healing functionality led to further, more significant enhancement of fatigue life.

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